

Exploring the Relationship between Spirituality and Health Outcomes in India: A Review

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Spirituality plays an important role in physical, psychological, and social health. Spirituality and its effect on health have gained attention for many years. It not only manages diseases in individuals but also acts as a preventive and protective factor for them. The present review aims to synthesize previous researches on the relationship between spirituality and health outcomes, and also identify research gaps in Indian studies. It synthesizes studies conducted in India that studied the relationship between spirituality and physical, psychological, and social health outcomes. Findings suggest that spirituality is significantly associated with better physical health, promotes psychological well-being, and improves social functioning. Higher levels of spirituality are linked to reduced stress, better coping abilities, improved psychological well-being, and enhanced quality of life. We also found that most Indian studies are cross-sectional in nature and rely primarily on self-report measures, which may increase the likelihood of response bias and limit causal interpretation. Future research should include other measures and focus on longitudinal and intervention-based studies within the Indian context to obtain a more detailed understanding of the role of spirituality in health.

Keywords: Spirituality, physical health, psychological health, social health, India

Spirituality lacks a single, universally accepted definition. In the Indian context, it often overlaps with religiosity, leading many to understand spirituality as same as religion. While religion typically involves rituals, scriptures, and pilgrimages, spirituality focuses on seeking search for meaning and purpose, self-acceptance, and self-realization (Pargament, 1997). It is considered a journey from outward experiences to inner understanding. Spirituality is subjective and personal, whereas religion is structured and institutionalized (Koenig, 2012). In the Indian context, spirituality involves showing respect, compassion, kindness, and love for all.

In the Indian context, spirituality encompasses inner peace, a sense of meaning and connectivity, which helps to improve our overall health (Subbarayappa, 2005). It also includes spiritual practices such as yoga and meditation, as well as religious experiences. It plays an important role in individual and collective life.

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Dimensions of Spirituality

Spirituality has multiple dimensions commonly associated with human experiences of the meaning of life, purpose, social connectedness, and curiosity (Hill et al., 2000). Research across psychology, sociology, and philosophy has described different dimensions of spirituality that helps to improve health.

Meaning and Purpose in Life

Spirituality helps to find meaning and purpose in life. This dimension refers to a person's ability to understand life experiences, find meaning in life, and have a sense of direction. It helps individuals to interpret suffering and adversity during stressful life events (Pargament, 1997). Research indicates that spirituality plays a central role and acts as a motivational force in achieving psychological resilience (Frankl, 1963). Higher levels of spirituality are connected with better health outcomes, which decreases vulnerability towards mental health problems and increases satisfaction about with life (Koenig et al., 2012).

Connectedness and Relationship

Connectedness is also a main dimension of spirituality, which describes the relation with oneself, others, and nature. This dimension means feeling of belongingness, empathy, and social harmony. Research indicates that people who feel spirituality have strong interpersonal relationships and better social support (Koenig, 2012). In India, spirituality is strongly connected with prayers, religious gatherings, and social rituals, which helps to enhance social harmony and emotional support (Singh, 1997).

Inner peace and Emotional harmony: Inner peace means a state of mental calmness, emotional balance and freedom from stress (Kabat-Zinn, 1994). This dimension is related to meditation, mindfulness and self-awareness. Walsh (2011) described that spiritual practice like meditation helps to decrease stress, anxiety, and emotional disturbances. Spiritual relaxation techniques help to reduce physiological stress responses and increase psychological

well-being (Benson & Proctor, 2010). In the Indian context, spiritual practices such as yoga and meditation help to maintain mental balance, self-control, which contributes to emotional stability and resilience (Kabat-Zinn, 2003).

Faith and Transcendence

Faith and transcendence are also main dimensions of spirituality, which involves belief in a higher power or reality outside the physical world. It provides individuals with optimism, hope, and coping resources during difficult situations (Pargament, 1997). Spiritual faith is associated with better coping strategies, decreased stress, and better mental health (Koenig et al., 2001). It helps individuals to deal with chronic illness and life challenges by increasing acceptance and optimism (George et al., 2000).

Health

WHO (1948) defines health as a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. It suggests that health is not limited to the absence of diseases, encompassing all domains, including physical, psychological, and social well-being. Physical health involves a balanced diet, getting sufficient sleep, engaging in regular exercise, and adopting healthy lifestyle habits. Psychological health includes proper cognition, emotional intelligence, life satisfaction, and well-being. Social health is reflected in building and sustaining supportive and healthy relationships with others. Physical fitness, mental health, and social relationships are interconnected and influence one another. An individual who is physically fit is able to cope with stressful situations in an adaptive manner and manage interpersonal relationships effectively (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Similarly, individuals with social support are better able to manage stressful situations and recover more easily from difficulties.

Spirituality is positively related to psychological well-being (Bozek et al., 2020; Coyle, 2002). Spiritual practices improve immunity, sleep patterns, and a healthy lifestyle. It focuses on self-awareness and self-acceptance, which promotes psychological health (Benson & Proctor, 2010). Also, it promotes forgiveness, compassion, and social support, which positively influences overall health (Worthington, 2005). Additionally, practices such as meditation and prayer may enhance well-being and provide coping mechanisms for life's stresses (Sharma & Misra, 2018).

Spirituality and Physical Health

In India, spirituality is associated with discipline, yoga, prayer, and service, which promote behaviors that lead to a healthy lifestyle (Koenig et al., 2012). Yoga improves balance, flexibility, and overall physical functioning. When integrated with meditation and mindfulness practices, yoga has been found to enhance overall well-being. Its beneficial effects have been observed in both clinical and non-clinical samples (Büssing et al., 2012). Several studies have found a connection between spirituality and physical health (Koenig et al., 2012; McCullough et al., 2000). The beneficial effects of spirituality have been observed in both clinical and non-clinical samples. It improves the quality of life for hospitalized patients, acting as an intrinsic motivational factor (Nandika et al., 2022). It motivates individuals to adopt healthy lifestyles through voluntary engagement. In older rural women, spiritual and religious engagement has been associated with better quality of life and enhanced perceived physical well-being (Krause, 2003). It promotes

balance in the body and reduces negative thought patterns (Kuril, 2022). The overall evidence supports the role of spirituality as an important factor contributing to physical health by promoting practices such as yoga and meditation, and by improving perceived physical health.

Spirituality and Psychological Health

Spirituality is not only associated with physical health but also with psychological health. It provides individuals with a sense of meaning, purpose, and hope, which acts as a protective with positive relationship has been found between spirituality, psychological capital, and psychological well-being (Madan & Rastogi, 2021). Psychological capital is a positive psychological resource consisting of hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism (Luthans et al., 2007). Spirituality enhances the self-efficacy of an individual as it emphasizes personal growth and inner strengths (Pargament, 1997). It provides individuals with a positive outlook and a renewed sense of meaning in life. Spirituality supports resilience, individuals bounce back from adversity through the adoption of healthy coping strategies (Masten, 2001). Spirituality provides a sense of meaning, purpose, and inner strengths, which enhances their ability to cope with stress (Park, 2010). Certain dimensions of spirituality play a particularly significant role; for example, existential well-being and hope are positively associated with quality of life among university students (Deb & Strodl, 2019). Spirituality is not only associated with psychological well-being but also helps reduce the impact of job stress (Mahipalan & Sheena, 2019). It guides the individual to adopt healthier coping strategies, which further contribute to psychological well-being.

Spirituality and Social Health

Spirituality plays a significant role in social health; it influences the relationship of an individual with oneself and others. It emphasizes values such as compassion, forgiveness, and connectedness, which strengthen their interpersonal relationships (Worthington, 2005). James (1902) proposed that spiritual experiences promote belongingness and moral responsibility toward others which enhances social functioning. Individuals engaged in spiritually oriented activities help individuals to develop social competence (Ellison & George, 1994). Higher spirituality is associated with healthier social behaviors and greater psychological well-being (Bozek et al., 2020). It enhances healthier coping mechanisms during interpersonal conflicts. Increased spiritual and religious participation can lead to better self-rated health outcomes among older adults (Roy et al., 2023). Spiritual practices foster forgiveness, compassion, kindness, and optimism, which help in developing healthy and supportive social relationships (McCullough et al., 2001).

Discussion

The present review shows a consistent and meaningful linkage between spirituality and various health domains, including physical, psychological, and social health (Webb, 2025). Spiritual practices including yoga, meditation, and mindfulness aid in adopting a healthy lifestyle and changing perceptions towards maladaptive behaviors. It improves resilience, hope, optimism, psychological flexibility, and quality of life, which fosters the psychological well-being of an individual. The review also found that spirituality strengthens relationships of an individual with others and oneself.

Spiritual values such as connectedness, forgiveness, and compassion foster social competence.

However, a strong positive association was found between spirituality and health. Several limitations have been found in the reviewed studies. Most Indian studies are cross-sectional in nature and rely primarily on self-report tools, which may increase the likelihood of response bias and limit causal explanation. There is also a lack of longitudinal and intervention-based studies, particularly in India.

Future research should include a mixed method approach and focus on longitudinal and intervention-based studies within the Indian context to obtain a more detailed understanding of the function of spirituality in health.

Overall, the review highlights the importance of integrating spirituality into holistic models of health and well-being. It suggests that spirituality can act as a psychosocial resource and may have important implications for health promotion, counseling, and community-based interventions, especially in culturally diverse populations.

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